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D4.1 - Institutional framework and gap analysis of regulation for natural hydrogen

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Table of contents

1.	Introduction	7
1.1	Objectives	7
1.2	Methodology	7
2.	Institutional framework - stakeholder mapping.....	9
2.1	Morocco	9
2.1.1	Interest / influence matrix.....	13
2.2	Mozambique	15
2.2.1	Interest / influence matrix.....	16
2.3	South Africa.....	18
2.3.1	Interest / influence matrix.....	20
2.4	Togo	23
2.4.1	Interest / influence matrix.....	26
3.	Mining and hydrocarbon regulatory framework	29
3.1	Morocco	29
3.2	Mozambique	30
3.3	South Africa.....	32
3.4	Togo.....	34
4.	Gap Analysis	35

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 - STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING: ROLES, INFLUENCE, AND INTEREST	8
FIGURE 2 – INFLUENCE/INTEREST MATRIX FOR MOROCCO’S STAKEHOLDERS	14
FIGURE 3 – INFLUENCE/INTEREST MATRIX FOR MOZAMBIQUE’S STAKEHOLDERS	17
FIGURE 4 – INFLUENCE/INTEREST MATRIX FOR SOUTH AFRICA’S STAKEHOLDERS	22
FIGURE 5 – INFLUENCE/INTEREST MATRIX FOR TOGO’S STAKEHOLDERS	27

List of tables

TABLE 1- STAKEHOLDER MAPPING IN MOROCCO	9
TABLE 2 - MOROCCO STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING INFLUENCE AND INTEREST	13
TABLE 3 - STAKEHOLDER MAPPING IN MOZAMBIQUE	15
TABLE 4 - MOZAMBIQUE STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING INFLUENCE AND INTEREST	16
TABLE 5 - STAKEHOLDER MAPPING IN SOUTH AFRICA	19
TABLE 6 - SOUTH AFRICAN STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING INFLUENCE AND INTEREST	20
TABLE 7 - STAKEHOLDER MAPPING IN TOGO	23
TABLE 8 - TOGO STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING INFLUENCE AND INTEREST	27

Summary

Local teams in Morocco, South Africa, Mozambique and Togo mapped the relevant institutions and stakeholders that are direct or indirect parts of the value chain of natural hydrogen. After identification of the right institutions and stakeholders, an in order to define stakeholder engagement strategies that will drive the internal and external processes for the integration of natural hydrogen in the energy mix of the target countries, each of the stakeholders was classified in terms of its interest in natural hydrogen and its national or regional influence to drive the sector.

The existing mining and hydrocarbon laws in each of the target countries was revised, namely any specific mentioning of hydrogen, to conduct an analysis of existing gaps in regulations that HyAfrica can help overcome in subsequent tasks of Work Package 4.

Keywords

Natural Hydrogen, Africa, stakeholder mapping, regulatory framework, gap analysis of regulation.

1. Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The objective of HyAfrica is to assess the resources of natural hydrogen in promising regions of four African countries (Morocco, Mozambique, South Africa, and Togo) and evaluate its social-economic impact if deployed as an energy source for local communities.

Hydrogen is an attractive, clean, sustainable energy source primarily produced via industry. At present, most reviews on hydrogen focus on the preparation and storage of hydrogen, while the development and utilization of natural hydrogen, from a geologic origin, is expected not only to greatly reduce the hydrogen cost, but also giving it another role, as a clean primary energy source and not merely as an energy carrier to store energy from renewable sources. Natural hydrogen has been discovered in many geological environments, such as in oceanic spreading ridges, transform faults, passive margins, convergent margins, and intraplate settings. The primary sources of the hydrogen include alterations in Fe (II)-containing rocks, the radiolysis of water, degassed magma, and the reaction of water- and silica-containing rocks during the mechanical fracturing. Hydrogen can appear in free gas; it can be adsorbed or trapped in inclusions (Wang, L., et al., 2023)*. Currently, natural hydrogen exploration is at very starting stages. In Africa it is anticipated that one of the drawbacks for the wide use of natural hydrogen is the lack of specific legislation associated with poor knowledge of the potential reserves and its usage.

This report is part of WP4 of HyAfrica, of which the main expected outcomes include:

1. Incentivized and mainstreamed in relevant policy and regulations leading to an increased role of H₂ in industry and other relevant policies in the target countries
2. Identifying the legal enablers for the key institutions that participate in the exploration and development of natural hydrogen deposits.
3. Identifying opportunities and possibilities for implementation of H₂ exploitation, with economic and social benefits.

Achieving these objectives implies mapping the relevant stakeholders in each country and the current regulatory framework under which natural hydrogen may in the future be considered. These are the main aims of current report.

1.2 Methodology

Each country was encouraged to identify their stakeholders

1. As a first step just a list of stakeholders was required;
2. A second step categorized the stakeholders can categorize by interest and motivation;

As a result, all relevant stakeholders were identified and their respective roles and functions analysed. Additionally, data was gathered based on secondary sources (e.g. official reports by government agencies and websites) to complement and verify the identification process.

*Wang, L., Jin, Z., Chen, X., Su, Y., & Huang, X. (2023). The Origin and Occurrence of Natural Hydrogen. *Energies*, 16(5), 2400. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16052400>

For the sake of clarity, stakeholders' mapping is divided into the following groups/categories:

- I. government and regulatory entities,
- II. private entities and resident firms, and
- III. other stakeholders (e.g. international development organizations).

The level of influence of the stakeholders on the decision-making process to contribute for energy transition and the level of their interest to advance this concept in the country is assessed according to scheme in Figure 1 and divided into the groups:

- i. **high influence – high interest:** this group of stakeholders should be regularly contacted and educated thoroughly on natural hydrogen related aspects;
- ii. **low influence – high interest:** stakeholder that HyAfrica should strive to keep informed about progress and encouraged to participate in workshops and raising awareness events
- iii. **high influence – low interest:** this group of stakeholders should be monitored closely and provided with information about the progress of the project;
- iv. **low influence – low interest:** the less relevant group of stakeholders, targeted to receive only key information about HyAfrica and natural hydrogen

Figure 1 - Stakeholders mapping: roles, influence, and interest

Each local team builds the influence-interest matrix and subsequent tasks in WP4 shall engage with the local stakeholders taking into account that matrix.

In parallel to the stakeholder mapping exercise, each local team identified the mining and petroleum regulations that are applicable in the target countries, in order to conduct a gap analysis aiming at clarifying if hydrogen is included (directly or indirectly) in the existing regulations.

2. Institutional framework - stakeholder mapping

2.1 Morocco

Morocco has identified fourteen stakeholders as possibly relevant for the natural hydrogen exploration, production and utilization in Morocco (Table 1).

Table 1- Stakeholder mapping in Morocco

Organization	Acronym	Website	Category
Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development	MTEDD	www.mem.gov.ma	Government
National Office of Hydrocarbons and Mines	ONHYM	www.onhym.com	Parastatal
University Mohamed Premier Oujda	UMP	www.ump.ma	Research Collaborator
University Mohammed VI Polytechnique	UM6P	um6p.ma	Possible Research Collaborator
Office Chérifien des Phosphates	OCP	www.ocpgroup.ma	Parastatal
Sound Energy		www.soundenergyplc.com	Private company
Hynat		hynat.com	Private company
Storengy		www.engie.com	Private company
Managem		www.managemgroup.com	Private company
Chariot Oil & Gas		chariotenergygroup.com	Private company
Moroccan Agency for Sustainable Energy	MASEN	www.masen.ma	Government
INNOV X		innovx.com	Private company
DAHAMCO			Private company
Power SUR SARL		www.powersurgelb.com	Private company

Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development

The Moroccan Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development plays a pivotal role in shaping and implementing the country's policies related to energy, sustainable development, and environmental preservation. The Ministry seeks to build a resilient and sustainable energy system, support Morocco's socio-economic development, and address global environmental challenges.

Currently, the available information indicates that the only direct involvement of the Moroccan Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development in natural hydrogen is that it granted ONHYM two exploration areas for their development. The Moroccan Ministry is actively involved in various renewable energy projects such as solar, wind and recently green hydrogen. **Key policymaker in resource exploration and energy transition.**

National Office of Hydrocarbons and Mines

The National Office of Hydrocarbons and Mines (ONHYM) is a Moroccan state-owned organization responsible for exploring, developing, and promoting the country's hydrocarbon and mineral resources. It oversees research and partnerships to unlock Morocco's potential in oil, gas, and mining industries while ensuring sustainable practices. ONHYM plays a key role in attracting investment and fostering economic growth in the energy and mining sectors.

ONHYM has been exploring for natural hydrogen in Morocco since 2017 where it showed the natural hydrogen potential in many areas of the country. ONHYM holds the only exclusive area granted by the ministry and is developing them with national and international partners. **Major stakeholder and leader of natural hydrogen exploration in Morocco.**

University Mohamed Premier Oujda

The University Mohamed Premier (UMP) in Oujda serves as a regional hub for higher education and research, offering diverse undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral programs across disciplines such as sciences, engineering, humanities, law, economics, and medicine. UMP is committed to fostering innovation and academic excellence, with a strong focus on research and development that addresses regional and national challenges.

The university actively collaborates with international institutions and industries to enhance academic exchange and technological innovation. Situated in eastern Morocco, UMP plays a vital role in supporting socio-economic development in the region by preparing skilled graduates and contributing to knowledge creation in key areas such as renewable energy, sustainable development, and digital transformation. UMP is also very active in natural hydrogen through its participation in the HyAfrica project for the evaluation of H₂ potential in the eastern zones of Morocco. **Partner in the HyAfrica project. Significant research interest, but limited influence in policymaking.**

University Mohammed VI Polytechnique

The University Mohammed VI Polytechnique (UM6P) is a leading institution focused on innovation, research, and sustainable development. Established in 2017, UM6P emphasizes STEM (Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines, agriculture, mining, and business while fostering entrepreneurship and addressing Africa's socio-economic challenges. Known for its state-of-the-art facilities and global partnerships, the university integrates education with cutting-edge research, positioning itself as a hub for transformative solutions and talent development in Morocco and beyond.

UM6P is actively involved in exploring natural hydrogen in the area of the coastal Meseta as part of its partnership with ONHYM to develop this area. **Significant research and exploration interest in the Khemisset basin in Morocco.**

Office Chérifien des Phosphates

The Office Chérifien des Phosphates (OCP) Group is a global leader in the phosphate industry, specializing in the extraction, production and export of phosphate-based fertilizers. Established in 1920, OCP plays a crucial role in global food security by providing sustainable agricultural solutions. The group is committed to innovation, environmental stewardship, and supporting economic development, particularly in Africa, through initiatives that promote soil health, efficient farming practices, and community empowerment.

The OCP Group is at the forefront of Morocco's green hydrogen strategy, leveraging its expertise in industrial innovation and sustainable practices. As a major consumer of ammonia, a key ingredient in phosphate fertilizer production, OCP aims to produce green ammonia using hydrogen derived from renewable energy. This aligns with Morocco's broader decarbonization goals and positions the country as a leader in the green hydrogen economy. Through strategic partnerships and investments in renewable energy infrastructure, OCP is driving the development of a sustainable hydrogen ecosystem, contributing to global efforts to transition to clean energy. **Leader of phosphates mining with influence on mining policy but prioritize other renewable energy solutions over hydrogen (Green hydrogen).**

Sound Energy

Sound Energy is a UK-based clean energy company focused on developing sustainable energy solutions, with significant operations in Morocco. The company specializes in natural gas exploration and production, with its flagship Tendrara project in eastern Morocco aimed at supplying cleaner energy to support the country's energy transition. Sound Energy is committed to fostering local economic growth and contributing to Morocco's goal of enhancing energy security and reducing carbon emissions through reliable and sustainable energy sources.

Sound Energy is exploring opportunities to integrate hydrogen into its operations as part of its commitment to sustainable energy solutions. In Morocco, the company has expressed interest in leveraging its existing natural gas infrastructure, such as the Tendrara project, to support the production and distribution of blue hydrogen. **Focuses on hydrocarbons sector with limited hydrogen exploration efforts.**

Hynat

Hynat is a Swiss company focused on advancing the exploration and development of natural hydrogen as a clean and sustainable energy source. It aims to position Morocco as a key player in the emerging natural hydrogen market by leveraging the country's potential. Hynat emphasizes research and innovation to unlock the potential of natural hydrogen, contributing to Morocco's energy transition and global decarbonization efforts. Their activity is focused on the Laayoune-Dakhla Basin in the Southern Provinces of Morocco. **Significant exploration interest in the southern provinces of Morocco.**

Storengy

Storengy, a subsidiary of ENGIE, is a global leader in the development and operation of underground natural gas storage facilities. With decades of expertise, Storengy specializes in designing, building, and managing storage solutions to ensure energy security and flexibility for its clients. The company also pioneers innovative projects in renewable energy, including natural hydrogen, geothermal energy, and biomethane, aligning with the global transition to sustainable energy.

Storengy is exploring for natural hydrogen in many regions in France and in the coastal meseta in Morocco, where it is in partnership with ONHYM. **Significant exploration interest in the Berrechid basin in Morocco.**

Managem

Managem is a Moroccan mining group with a strong presence in Africa, specializing in the exploration, extraction, and production of a diverse range of metals and minerals, including cobalt, copper, silver, and gold. Committed to sustainable and responsible mining, Managem integrates innovation and environmental practices into its operations. The group

plays a key role in supporting the energy transition through its focus on strategic minerals critical to renewable energy technologies and electric mobility.

Managem could also be interested by hydrogen since it acquired 55% of the Sound Energy natural gas concession of Tendirara in the East of Morocco. **Key mining company with strong political and economic influence but less direct interest in hydrogen utilization.**

Chariot Oil & Gas

Chariot Oil & Gas is an Africa-focused energy company specializing in sustainable energy solutions. Initially recognized for its oil and gas exploration activities, Chariot has evolved to prioritize renewable energy and natural gas projects. The company is committed to providing affordable and reliable energy to support economic growth and energy transition in its operational regions.

Chariot is also involved in green hydrogen projects in Morocco and Mauritania. Their first pilot is currently under development at OCP's Jorf Lasfar industrial site in Northern Morocco, in partnership with UM6P and Oort Energy. **Focuses on hydrocarbons sector with unknown hydrogen exploration efforts.**

Moroccan Agency for Sustainable Energy

The Moroccan Agency for Sustainable Energy (Masen) is a leading organization driving Morocco's transition to renewable energy. Established in 2010, Masen develops and manages large-scale solar, wind, and hydroelectric projects, including the Noor Ouarzazate Solar Complex, one of the world's largest solar power plants. Masen aims to increase renewable energy's share in Morocco's energy mix, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and enhance energy security. The agency plays a pivotal role in advancing clean energy solutions.

Masen is actively exploring the potential of green hydrogen as part of Morocco's commitment to renewable energy and sustainable development. Leveraging its expertise in solar, wind, and hydro projects, Masen is positioning Morocco as a key player in the emerging green hydrogen economy. The agency collaborates with international partners to develop green hydrogen production facilities powered by renewable energy, aiming to produce clean hydrogen for domestic use and export. **Key actor of the energy transition policy but prioritize other renewable energy solutions.**

INNOV X

Innov X is an organization focused on fostering innovation and delivering cutting-edge solutions across industries. Specializing in advanced technologies, research, and development, Innov X drives progress in fields such as renewable energy, digital transformation, and sustainable practices. By combining expertise with a forward-thinking approach, the company empowers businesses to adapt to evolving challenges and seize new opportunities.

Innov X is at the forefront of advancing hydrogen technologies, focusing on developing innovative solutions for the production, storage, and utilization of clean hydrogen energy. By leveraging cutting-edge research and strategic collaborations, Innov X aims to drive the adoption of hydrogen as a key pillar of the energy transition. The company explores green hydrogen production methods powered by renewable energy and supports its integration into industries like transportation, manufacturing, and energy storage. **Significant innovation interest, but limited influence in policymaking and implementation.**

DAHAMCO

Based in Dakhla, in the Southern Provinces, then private company Dahamco stated ambition is to “develop renewable fuels for a better future”. There is little information about the company. The only information available concerns the establishment of a green hydrogen and ammonia production plant extending over an area of 553,435 ha, for an investment of 254 million DHM and a prospect of 3,100 jobs to be created. **Mainly focused on green hydrogen projects.**

Power SUR SARL

Power SUR is a Morocco-based energy company dedicated to advancing sustainable energy solutions. The company is spearheading a green hydrogen project in Morocco, it was granted a site, in the Dakhla region, dedicated to the production of green on an area of 15,000 ha, for an investment of 19.5 billion dirhams, and should generate 650 jobs. **Mainly focused on green hydrogen projects.**

2.1.1 Interest / influence matrix

Table 2 and Figure 2 depict the interest and influence of each stakeholder, including possible engagement in WP4 activities.

Table 2 - Morocco stakeholders mapping influence and interest

Organization	Classification	Action
Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development	High Interest - High Influence	Contact regularly and educate thoroughly
National office of hydrocarbons and mines		
University Mohammed VI Polytechnique		
Hynat		
Storengy		
Office Chérifien des phosphates	Low Interest - High Influence	Keep in the loop and encourage to participate
Moroccan Agency for Sustainable Energy		
University Mohamed Premier Oujda	High Interest - Low Influence	Monitor closely and give access to information
INNOV X		
Chariot Oil & Gas	Low Interest - Low Influence	Check in occasionally and provide key information
Sound Energy		
Managem		
DAHAMCO		
Power SUR SARL		

Figure 2 – Influence/Interest matrix for Morocco’s stakeholders

2.2 Mozambique

Twenty one stakeholders were identified for Mozambique who could potentially play a relevant role in the exploration and exploitation of natural hydrogen in Mozambique are listed in Table 3. Each of the listed stakeholders are divided into the following groups:

- **Possible research collaborators** encompass academic institutions currently involved in research on the geological occurrences of geological hydrogen. Examples include the CSOGET (Centro Regional de Excelência em Estudos de Engenharia e Tecnologia de Petróleo e Gás da Universidade Eduardo Mondlane), the Geology Department, Faculty of Sciences, UEM, the Center for Research in Energies, Faculty of Sciences, UEM
- **National electricity regulator**, ARENE, is responsible for the regulation of electricity in Mozambique. Its mandate falls under the Electricity Regulation Law, (Law N.º 12/2022 of 11 of July), and Petroleum (Law no. 21/2014 of 18 August).
- **Government Department** that may have interest in natural hydrogen sources are MIREME, National Directorate of Hydrocarbon, National Directorate of Mines and Geology (DNGM), National Institute of Petroleum (INP), Energy Fund (FUNAE) and APIEX.
- **Parastatal**, EDM is the primary electricity provider (distribution) in Mozambique with a market-share of more than 46% in the country. They serve as an exporter to neighbouring countries, supplying energy into the South African Power Pool. ENH (National Oil Company) is responsible for the upstream and downstream activities in the hydrocarbon sector
- **Private (international and national) Sector**. The exploration and exploitation of natural hydrogen is of interest to the private sector as a potential area to expand or invest into. This includes TotalEnergies (IOC), Coral FLNG (operated by ENI), EXXON Mobil, SASOL, PUMA Energy, and Matola Gas Company.
- **Professional Association**, AGMM, AMER (Associação Moçambicana de Energias Renováveis), CMM (Chamber of Mines of Mozambique), and Confederation of Economic Associations (CTA).

Table 3 - Stakeholder mapping in Mozambique

Organization	Acronym	Website	Category
Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy	MIREME	mis.mireme.gov.mz	Government Departments
National Directorate of Hydrocarbon	DNH		Government Departments
National Directorate of Mines and Geology	DNGM	mis.mireme.gov.mz/DNGM	Government Departments
National Institute of Petroleum	INP	www.inp.gov.mz	Government Departments
Energy Fund	FUNAE	funae.co.mz	Parastatal
Energy Regulatory Authority	ARENE	arene.org.mz	Government Departments
Investment and Export Promotion Agency	APIEX	apiex.gov.mz	Government Departments
University Eduardo Mondlane	UEM	uem.moz	Research
Electricity of Mozambique	EDM	www.edm.co.mz	Parastatal

Organization	Aacronym	Website	Category
National Hydrocarbons Company	ENH (National Oil Company)	www.enh.co.mz	Parastatal
TotalEnergies		totalenergies.com/mozambique	Int. Private Sector
Coral FLNG			Int. Private Sector
EXXON Mobil		www.exxonmobil.co.mz	Int. Private Sector
SASOL		www.sasol.com/mozambique	Int. Private Sector
Mozambique LNG		www.mozambiqueLng.co.mz	Private Sector
PUMA Energy		pumaenergy.com	Int. Private Sector
Matola Gas Company		www.mgc.co.mz	Private Sector
Geological Mining Association of Mozambique	AGMM		Prof. Association
Mozambican Renewable Energy Association	AMER	amer.org.mz	Prof. Association
Mining Chamber of Mozambique	CMM	www.cmm.org.mz	Prof. Association
Confederation of Economic Associations of Mozambique	CTA	cta.org.mz	Prof. Association

2.2.1 Interest / influence matrix

The matrix representing the interest and influence of each of the entities listed in Table 3 is provided in Table 4 and in Figure 3, as well as the actions to be taken in subsequent tasks of WP4.

Table 4 - Mozambique stakeholders mapping influence and interest

Organization	Influence / Interest	Action
Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy	High Influence - High Interest	Contact regularly and educate thoroughly
National Directorate of Hydrocarbon		
National Directorate of Mines and Geology		
National Institute of Petroleum		
Energy Fund		
Autoridade Reguladora de Energia		
University Eduardo Mondlane		
Electricity of Mozambique	Low Influence - High Interest	Keep in the loop and encourage to participate
National Oil Company		
Associação Moçambicana de Energias Renováveis		
Matola Gas Company	High Influence - Low Interest	Monitor closely and give access to information
APIEX		
Mozambican Geological and Mining Association	Low Influence - Low Interest	Check in occasionally and provide key information
TotalEnergies		
Coral FLNG		

Organization	Influence / Interest	Action
EXXON Mobil		
SASOL		
Mozambique LNG		
PUMA Energy		
Mozambican Mining chamber		
Confederation of Economic Associations		

Figure 3 – Influence/Interest matrix for Mozambique’s stakeholders

2.3 South Africa

The forty-four stakeholders identified for South Africa who could potentially play a role in the exploration and exploitation of natural hydrogen in South Africa are listed in Table 5. Each of the listed stakeholders are divided into the following groups:

- **Possible research collaborators** encompass academic institutions currently involved in research on the geological occurrences of geological hydrogen.
- **Funders** include SANEDI providing financial support to the currently LEAP-RE HyAfrica project.
- **Science Councils** are research institutions and repositories of scientific information. Collaboration with these Councils is essential.
- **National electricity regulator**, NERSA, is responsible for the regulation of electricity, piped gas and petroleum pipeline industries in South Africa. This mandate falls under the Electricity Regulation Act, 2006 (Act No. 4 of 2006), Gas Act, 2001 (Act No. 48 of 2001) and Petroleum Pipelines Act, 2003 (Act No. 60 of 2003).
- **Government agencies** that may have a vested interest in natural hydrogen sources are DSTI, DTIC and IDC (responsible for the development and growth of science, technology and industry in the country), department for the protection and equitable distribution of resources (e.g. DWS, DMR, CEF and DFFE). The current research area falls under the jurisdiction of the Mpumalanga Provincial Government. The Presidential Climate Commission reports and advice the Office of the President on matters of low carbons emissions and building a climate-resilient economy. This Commission also serves as an intermediary between different parties working towards this same goal.
- **Parastatal**, ESKOM, is the primary electricity provider (generation and dissemination) in South Africa with a market-share of more than 80%. They serve as an exporter to neighbouring countries, supplying eight Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) with regular or on-demand electricity.
- **Private Sector**. The exploration and exploitation of natural hydrogen is of interest to the private sector as a potential area to expand or invest into.
- **Consulting / Financing**. Future development of natural hydrogen in South Africa will require substantial investment from consulting and other financial institutions. The list of a few potentially interested companies, listed in the table below, is not exhaustive.

Table 5 - Stakeholder mapping in South Africa

Organization	Acronym	Website	Category
University of Pretoria	UP	up.ac.za	Possible Research Collaborator
Energy Economics Research Unit	EERU - UP	up.ac.za/energy-economics-research-unit	Possible Research Collaborator
University of Limpopo	UL	ul.ac.za	Possible Research Collaborator
Hydrogen Systems South Africa	HySA	hysasystems.com	Possible Research Collaborator
South African National Energy Development Institute	SANEDI	sanedi.org.za	HyAfrica South African funder
Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy	LEAP-RE	leap-re.eu	UEU Project Funder
Council for Geoscience	CGS	geoscience.org.za	Science Council
Council for Scientific Innovation and Research	CSIR	csir.co.za	Science Council
Minerals Council South Africa		mineralscouncil.org.za	Science Council
Council for Mineral Technology	MINTEK	mintek.co.za	Science Council
Mine Health and Safety Council	MHSC	mhsc.org.za	Science Council
Technology Innovation Agency	TIA	tia.org.za	Science Council
Water Research Commission	WRC	wrc.org.za	Science Council
National Energy Regulator of South Africa	NERSA	nersa.org.za	Regulator
Department of Water and Sanitation	DWS	dws.gov.za	Government
Department of Mineral Resources and Energy	DMRE	dmr.gov.za	Government
Dept Economic Development, Environmental Affairs and Tourism			Government
Central Energy Fund	CEF	cefgroup.co.za	Government
Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment	DFFE	dffe.gov.za	Government
Department of Science, Technology and Innovation	DSTI	dsti.gov.za	Government
Department of Trade Industry and Competition	DTIC	thedtic.gov.za	Government
Industrial Development Corporation	IDC	idc.co.za	Government
Mpumalanga Provincial Government		mpg.gov.za	Government
Presidential Climate Commission		climatecommission.org.za	Government
Eskom	ESKOM	eskom.co.za	Parastatal
Sasol	SASOL	sasol.com	Private sector
Minerals Education Trust Fund	METF	metf.co.za	Private sector
Thungela		thungela.com	Private sector
Exxaro		exxaro.com	Private sector
AngloAmerican		angloamerican.com	Private sector
Engie Africa		engie-africa.com	Private sector

Organization	Acronym	Website	Category
Environmental Resources Management	ERM	erm.com	Private sector
Hydrox Holdings		hydroxholdings.co.za	Private sector
Earthlife Africa		earthlife.org.za	NGO
Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials	RSB	rsb.org	NGO*
World Wildlife Fund	WWF	worldwildlife.org	NGO
African Hydrogen Partnership	AHP	ahp.africa	NGO
United Nations Development Fund	UNDP	undp.org	Development Finance Organisation
African Development Bank		afdb.org	Development Finance Organisation
NEPAD Business Foundation	NBF	nepadbusinessfoundation.org	Multilateral organisation
PriceWaterhouseCooper	PWC	pwc.co.za	Consulting
KPMG Southern Africa	KPMG	kpmg.com/za	Consulting
Development Bank of Southern Africa	DBSA	dbsa.org	Consulting / Financing
Rand Merchant Bank	RMB	rmb.co.za	Consulting / Financing

2.3.1 Interest / influence matrix

The matrix representing the interest and influence of each of the entities is provided in Table 6 and in Figure 4.

Table 6 - South African stakeholders mapping influence and interest

Organization name	Influence / Interest	Action
Council for Geoscience	High Influence - High Interest	Contact regularly and educate thoroughly
Minerals Council South Africa		
Department of Mineral Resources and Energy		
University of Pretoria	Low Influence - High Interest	Keep in the loop and encourage to participate
University of Limpopo		
Energy Economics Research Unit		
Hydrogen Systems South Africa		
South African National Energy Development Institute		
Projektträger Jülich		
Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy		
Dept Economic Development, Environmental Affairs and Tourism		
Central Energy Fund		

Organization name	Influence / Interest	Action
Department of Science, Technology and Innovation		
Department of Trade Industry and Competition		
Industrial Development Corporation		
Mpumalanga Provincial Government		
Eskom		
Sasol		
Minerals Education Trust Fund		
Thungela		
Exxaro		
AngloAmerican		
Environmental Resources Management		
African Hydrogen Partnership		
Council for Scientific Innovation and Research		
Council for Mineral Technology		
Mine Health and Safety Council		
Technology Innovation Agency		
Water Research Commission		
National Energy Regulator of South Africa		
Department of Water and Sanitation		
Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment		
Presidential Climate Commission		
Engie		
Hydrox		
Earthlife Africa		
Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials		
World Wildlife Fund		
United Nations Development Fund		
African Development Bank		
NEPAD Business Foundation		
PriceWaterhouseCooper South Africa		
KPMG Southern Africa		
Development Bank of Southern Africa		
Rand Merchant Bank		

Figure 4 – Influence/Interest matrix for South Africa’s stakeholders

2.4 Togo

Table 7 lists the thirteen stakeholder identified as possibly relevant for the natural hydrogen exploration, production and utilization in Togo.

Table 7 - Stakeholder mapping in Togo

Organization	Acronym	Website	Category
Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources			Government
National Agency for Environmental Management	ANGE	Ange.tg	Government
University of Lomé		univ-lome.tg	Research Collaborator
Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency of ECOWAS	ECREEE	www.ecreee.org	Possible Research Collaborator
Togo Electric Power Company	CEET		Parastatal
Togolese Agency for Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy	AT2ER	at2er.tg	Parastatal
Economic Community of West African States	ECOWAS	hynat.com	Private company
West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use	WASCAL	www.ecowas.int	Possible Research Collaborator
Société Nouvelle des Phosphates du Togo	SNPT		Parastatal
Mining Governance and Development Project	PDGM		Possible Research Collaborator
Total Energies Togo		totalenergies.com/togo	Private company
Vivo Energy Togo		www.vivoenergy.com	Private company
Addax Petroleum		www.addaxpetroleum.com	Private company

Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources

The Togolese Ministry for Mines and Energy Resources is responsible for defining and coordinating the implementation of state policy in the fields of mining and energy. The Ministry oversees the exploration, extraction, and management of mineral and energy resources, ensuring sustainable development and compliance with regulations. It also focuses on improving energy access, promoting renewable energy, and enhancing energy efficiency across the country.

Currently, there is no specific information available about the direct involvement of Togo's Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources in hydrogen projects. However, the Ministry is actively involved in various renewable energy initiatives and projects aimed at improving energy access and sustainability in Togo. These efforts include the promotion of solar, wind, and other renewable energy sources, which could potentially pave the way for future involvement in hydrogen projects as part of the broader strategy to enhance the country's energy mix and reduce carbon emissions.

National Agency for Environmental Management

The Togo National Agency for Environmental Management (ANGE) is responsible for implementing national environmental policies and regulations and ensuring compliance with environmental standards through regular monitoring and assessment.

ANGE focus on pollution control and promoting sustainable management and conservation of natural resources, including forests, water bodies, and biodiversity. The agency conducts environmental impact assessments for proposed projects to ensure they meet environmental standards and regulations. Furthermore, ANGE develops and implements strategies to mitigate and adapt to the impacts of climate change.

There is no specific information available about the direct involvement of Togo's National Agency for Environmental Management (ANGE) in hydrogen projects.

University of Lomé

The University of Lomé is the largest public university in the country. It offers a wide range of programs across various disciplines, including sciences, humanities, social sciences, and professional studies. The University is actively involved in the mining and energy sectors through various initiatives and programs. One notable project is the Mining Governance and Development Project (PDGM), backed by the World Bank. This project has invested CFA700 million in training at the University of Lomé, focusing on improving the skills and logistics of both lecturers and students through practical work and the rehabilitation of lecture halls. The university has also launched new bachelor's degrees in mining geology and analytical chemistry with a focus on mining and the environment.

Regarding their involvement in hydrogen, the University of Lomé is actively engaged in the field through its participation in the International Master Programme in Energy and Green Hydrogen (IMP-EGH). This program, supported by the West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use (WASCAL), focuses on preparing the next generation of professionals to address energy challenges related to climate change in West Africa. The program includes specializations in bioenergy, biofuels, and green hydrogen technology.

Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency of ECOWAS

The ECOWAS Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (ECREEE) is a specialized agency of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Established in 2010, ECREEE is headquartered in Praia, Cape Verde. Its primary mission is to promote renewable energy and energy efficiency across the ECOWAS region. ECREEE's objectives include coordinating projects and programs related to renewable energy (RE) and energy efficiency (EE), improving access to modern energy services, and enhancing energy security. ECREEE plays a crucial role in realizing the ECOWAS Vision 2050, which emphasizes economic integration, interconnectivity, and sustainable development.

ECREEE is actively involved in promoting green hydrogen as part of its broader mandate to enhance renewable energy and energy efficiency in the West African region. It has established a Green Hydrogen Program, to develop and implement strategies for the production and utilization of green hydrogen within the ECOWAS member states. One of the key initiatives under this program is the Green Hydrogen Regional Strategy and Action Plans for 2023-2030 and 2031-2050. These plans focus on enhancing collaboration and cooperation among member states and partners to operationalize green hydrogen projects. The program includes efforts to review and assess ongoing collaboration efforts, as well as to formulate orientations to drive the implementation of the regional strategy.

Togo Electric Power Company

The Togo Electric Power Company, known as *Compagnie Energie Electrique du Togo* (CEET), is the primary entity responsible for the generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity in Togo. It plays a crucial role in the country's energy sector. CEET's responsibilities include maintaining and expanding the electrical infrastructure, managing the national grid, and implementing projects to improve access to electricity across Togo.

The company is also involved in various initiatives to enhance energy efficiency and promote the use of renewable energy sources. One of their notable projects is the TINGA Fund, which aims to increase electricity access in underserved regions, particularly in the Savanes and Kara areas.

Currently, there is no specific information available about the Togo Electric Power Company's (CEET) direct involvement in hydrogen projects.

Togolese Agency for Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy

The Togolese Agency for Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy (*L'Agence togolaise de l'électrification rurale et des énergies renouvelables*, AT2ER) is a key player in promoting sustainable energy solutions in Togo. The association brings together various stakeholders, including companies, NGOs, and other organizations, to coordinate actions and foster partnerships in the renewable energy sector. AT2ER aims to support the implementation of Togo's energy policy by creating synergies among its members and collaborating with national and international entities.

Regarding their involvement in hydrogen, there is no specific information available about AT2ER's direct engagement in hydrogen projects. However, given their focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency, it is possible that they may explore hydrogen as a potential area of interest in the future, especially considering the growing global emphasis on green hydrogen as a sustainable energy source.

Economic Community of West African States - ECOWAS

The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) plays a significant role in Togo to enhance trade and economic cooperation between and other member states, facilitating the free movement of goods, services, and people across borders. The organization is also actively involved in maintaining peace and security in Togo, supporting conflict prevention, management, and resolution efforts to ensure stability in the region. In the energy sector, ECOWAS, through the ECOWAS Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (ECREEE), previously described.

Regarding hydrogen, ECOWAS has developed a Green Hydrogen Policy and Strategy Framework to promote the development and utilization of green hydrogen within the region. This framework aims to position the ECOWAS region as a competitive producer and supplier of green hydrogen, addressing socio-economic growth and sustainable development. ECREEE has taken a lead in this process, collaborating with governments, private sector stakeholders, and international organizations to implement the policy, build necessary infrastructure, and foster research and development in green hydrogen technologies.

West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use

The West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use (WASCAL) is a research-focused Climate Service Centre designed to address climate change challenges in West Africa. Its mission is to provide information and knowledge at local, national, and regional levels to help West African countries cope with the adverse impacts of climate change. WASCAL collaborates with universities, research institutions, and governments across the region to develop sustainable adaptation strategies and promote resilient land use practices.

Regarding their involvement in hydrogen, WASCAL is actively engaged in promoting green hydrogen through the above-mentioned International Master's Programme in Energy and Green Hydrogen (IMP-EGH).

Société Nouvelle des Phosphates du Togo

The Société Nouvelle des Phosphates du Togo (SNPT) is a key player in Togo's mining sector, primarily responsible for the extraction, transport, processing, and marketing of phosphate. Phosphate is a crucial mineral for various industries, including agriculture, where it is used in fertilizers. As of now there is no specific information about SNPT's direct involvement in hydrogen projects.

Mining Governance and Development Project

The Mining Governance and Development Project (PDGM) in Togo is an initiative backed by the World Bank aimed at improving the governance and management of the mining sector. The primary objective of the project is to streamline the institutional arrangements of key organizations in the extractive industries to enhance their efficiency and accountability. There is no specific information available about the PDGM's direct involvement in hydrogen projects.

Total Energies Togo

Total Togo is a subsidiary of TotalEnergies, a multinational oil and gas company. Total Togo is involved in the distribution of petroleum products, including fuels and lubricants, across Togo. Regarding their involvement in hydrogen, TotalEnergies, the parent company, is actively engaged in the development and promotion of hydrogen, particularly green hydrogen. TotalEnergies has been investing in hydrogen infrastructure and projects globally, including the establishment of hydrogen refueling stations and partnerships to advance hydrogen technologies. While there is no specific information available about Total Togo's direct involvement in hydrogen projects, it is possible that they may benefit from the broader initiatives and expertise of TotalEnergies in this area.

Vivo Energy Togo

Vivo Energy Togo operates under the Shell brand and is involved in the distribution of fuels and lubricants across Togo. There is no specific information available about Vivo Energy Togo's direct engagement in hydrogen projects. However, the broader Vivo Energy group is exploring various sustainable energy solutions, including the potential for green hydrogen, as part of their commitment to energy transition and reducing carbon emissions. This indicates a possible future interest in hydrogen-related projects, aligning with global trends towards cleaner energy sources.

Addax Petroleum

Addax Petroleum, a subsidiary of the Sinopec Group, is an international oil and gas exploration and production company with operations in Africa, the Middle East, and Europe. In Togo, Addax Petroleum is involved in the exploration and production of oil and gas, contributing to the country's hydrocarbon sector. As of now, there is no specific information available about Addax Petroleum's direct involvement in hydrogen projects.

2.4.1 Interest / influence matrix

Table 8 and Figure 5 depict the interest and influence of each stakeholder, including possible engagement in WP4 activities.

Table 8 - Togo stakeholders mapping influence and interest

Organization	Classification	Action
Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources	High Interest - High Influence	Contact regularly and educate thoroughly
Togo Electric Power Company		
Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency of ECOWAS		
University of Lomé	High Interest - Low Influence	Keep in the loop and encourage to participate
Togolese Agency for Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy		
West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use		
National Agency for Environmental Management		
Economic Community of West African States	Low Interest - High Influence	Monitor closely and give access to information
Société Nouvelle des Phosphates du Togo		
Mining Governance and Development Project	Low Interest - Low Influence	Check in occasionally and provide key information
Total Energies Togo		
Vivo Energy Togo		
Addax Petroleum		

High Interest - High Influence

1. **Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources**
 - Key policymaker in resource exploration and energy transitions.
2. **Togo Electric Power Company**
 - Major stakeholder in energy supply and potential user of hydrogen for energy generation.
3. **Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency of ECOWAS**
 - Regional driver of renewable energy adoption, likely a promoter of hydrogen technologies.

High Interest - Low Influence

1. **University of Lomé**
 - Significant research interest, but limited influence in policymaking or large-scale implementation.
2. **Togolese Agency for Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy**
 - Advocacy-focused group likely interested in natural hydrogen but constrained in shaping high-level decisions.
3. **West African Science Service Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use**
 - Focuses on climate-related solutions, including potential applications of green hydrogen.
4. **National Agency for Environmental Management**
 - Environmental oversight ensures sustainability of exploration projects but has indirect influence on energy policy.

Low Interest - High Influence

1. **Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)**
 - Regional powerhouse with influence on energy policy but may prioritize other renewable energy solutions over hydrogen.
2. **Société Nouvelle des Phosphates du Togo**
 - Key mining company with strong political and economic influence but less direct interest in hydrogen utilization.

Low Interest - Low Influence

1. **Mining Governance and Development Project**
 - Focuses on mining sector governance with little direct relevance to hydrogen exploration.
2. **Total Togo**
 - While influential in the energy sector, its primary interest is fossil fuels unless transitioning to green energy.
3. **Vivo Energy Togo**
 - Similar to Total Togo, mainly focused on traditional energy products.
4. **Addax Petroleum**
 - Petroleum-focused, unlikely to prioritize natural hydrogen unless part of a broader shift.

3. Mining and hydrocarbon regulatory framework

3.1 Morocco

Morocco's regulatory framework for mining and hydrocarbon exploration is designed to attract investment while ensuring sustainable management of resources.

In the mining sector, the primary legislation is the Mining Code (Law No. 33-13), which came into effect in 2016, replacing the 1951 Mining Code. This law modernizes the sector, encouraging private investment and introducing clear procedures for exploration and exploitation. Exploration permits cover a surface of 16 km² and are valid for three years, renewable under specific conditions for an additional 4-year period, while exploitation licenses are issued for 10 years, renewable for successive 10-year periods. The framework also includes royalties based on mineral type and extraction levels, alongside corporate tax incentives for operations in remote areas. Environmental protection is a key aspect, with mandatory environmental impact assessments (EIAs) and post-mining restoration obligations. The National Office of Hydrocarbons and Mines (ONHYM) and the Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development play central roles in managing the mining sector.

In the hydrocarbon sector, the Hydrocarbon Code (Law No. 21-90), updated by Law No. 27-99, governs the exploration and exploitation of oil and natural gas. It provides incentives such as tax exemptions for up to 10 years and flexible production-sharing agreements (PSAs). Exploration permits are granted for up to eight years, while exploitation concessions are valid for 25 years, extendable by 10 years. ONHYM acts as the key institutional body, granting licenses, managing partnerships, and often retaining a minority stake in projects.

Morocco's favorable investment climate is further supported by its competitive tax regime, including corporate tax holidays for mining and hydrocarbon investments in designated regions.

Both sectors are underpinned by strong environmental and social governance requirements, mandating compliance with national and international standards. Companies must conduct EIAs and involve local communities in project development. International partnerships are actively encouraged, fostering technology transfer and capacity building.

Currently, Morocco does not have a dedicated regulatory framework specifically for natural hydrogen exploration and production. However, the country's interest in this emerging resource is growing, especially given its emphasis on sustainable energy transition and its interesting potential for hydrogen deposits. Talks started between ONHYM and the Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development to integrate Hydrogen exploration in the mining law amendment, but to this day no visibility is given on the subject.

Integration of natural hydrogen to the mining law seems the more adequate as this law is subject to an ongoing amendment in addition to the fact that the Moroccan mining code is not exclusive to traditional mining activities but includes also other commodities such as:

- Solid fossil fuels, graphite, as well as oil shales, bituminous limestones, and bituminous sands;
- Carbon dioxide gas;
- Spoil heaps and mine tailings;
- Underground saline waters;
- Geothermal deposits.

3.2 Mozambique

The key legal framework for mining activities in Mozambique is the Mining Law (Law 20/2014, of 18 August 2014, as amended), which establishes the general principles governing the award and exercise of mineral rights, and the Mining Law Regulations (Decree 31/2015, of 31 December 2015, as amended), which establish the rules for prospecting and exploration operations, development, processing and mining, as well as geological mapping, geological mining, and metallurgical and scientific studies.

In addition to the above, the mining sector is also governed by:

- the Regulations on the Marketing of Mineral Products (Decree 20/2011, of 1 July 2011, as amended);
- the Regulations on the Marketing of Diamonds, Precious Metals and Gems (Decree 63/2021, of 1 September 2021);
- the Regulations on the Inspection Activity of Mineral Resources and Energy (Decree 34/2019, of 2 May 2019);
- the Mining Labour Regulations (Decree 13/2015, of 3 July 2015);
- the Regulations on the Employment of Foreign Citizens for the Petroleum and Mining Sector (Decree 63/2011, of 7 December 2011);
- the Technical Safety and Health Regulations for Geological and Mineral Activity (Decree 61/2006, of 26 December 2006, as amended);
- the Regulations on the National Salvage and Rescue System for the Extractive Industry of Mineral Resources (Decree 32/2019, of 29 April 2019);
- the Environmental Regulations for Mineral Activities (Decree 26/2004, of 20 August 2004);
- the Basic Rules on Environmental Management for Mineral Activities (Ministerial Order 189/2006, of 14 December 2006);
- the Law on Public-Private Partnerships, Large-Scale Enterprises and Business Concessions (Law 15/2011, of 10 August 2011);
- the Regulations on Public-Private Partnerships, Large-Scale Enterprises and Business Concessions (Decree 16/2012, of 4 June 2012);
- the Taxation and Fiscal Benefits Regime of Mineral Operations (Law 28/2014, of 23 September 2014, as amended and republished) and its Regulations (Decree 28/2015, of 28 December 2015, as amended);
- model declarations necessary for compliance with tax obligations under the Regulations of Taxation and Fiscal Benefits Regime of Mineral Operations (Ministerial Order 37/2020, of 30 July 2020); and
- the VAT Refund Regulations (Decree 78/2017, of 28 December 2017, as amended) which provide for a special value-added tax regime for petroleum and mining companies in the production stage.

The Mozambique Mining Law No. 20/2014 regulates the use and exploitation of mineral resources in Mozambique. The regulatory framework for the sector includes the amendments to the Mining Law (Decree No. 48/2022) and to the Regulation of the Mining Law (Decree No. 48/2022), the Environmental Regulation for Mining Activity (approved by Decree No. 26/2004, of December 31), and the Regulation of the Mining Law (approved by Decree No. 31/2015, of December 31). Other substantive laws within the regulatory

framework for the mining sector can be found below. The Mining Law is available on the official website of the government (<https://mis.mireme.gov.mz>). The official version of the primary law is in Portuguese and there are no official translations of this law into other languages. The government regulating entity is the Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy (<https://mis.mireme.gov.mz>).

Mozambique has not yet adopted specific legislative initiatives related to energy-transition minerals.

Law nr. 21/2014 ("Petroleum Law") was published in the Official Gazette on 18 August, revoking, respectively, Law nr. 14/2002, of 26 June, and Law nr. 3/2001, of 21 February, and all other contravening legislation. This diploma entered in force on the date of their publication. In the context of significant discoveries of mineral resources and hydrocarbon reserves, these long-awaited pieces of legislation are expected to provide a comprehensive and updated legal framework for the mining and petroleum activities, even though regulation is still required – in 90 days, for the Mining Law, and in 60 days, for the Petroleum Law. The Mining Law seeks to ensure "fair" earnings for Mozambique and increase the control over mining activities. Any transfer of control – whether direct or indirect – in mining holding permits is now subject to the consent of the Mozambican Government. In addition, it is created the *Instituto Nacional de Minas* (National Mining Institute), a regulatory body under the Ministry of Mineral Resources, which will be responsible for overseeing the mining activity. The Petroleum Law is focused on reinforcing the role of the State – and of the State-owned company ENH, E.P. – in all petroleum activities. Also, a 25% share of the production obtained in Mozambican territory shall be reserved to the domestic market.

A general concern with local communities may be easily spotted in both diplomas: namely, not only a percentage of the earnings resulting from mining and petroleum production shall be allocated to the development of the affected local communities, but also it is required that a memorandum of understanding is executed with the local communities as a condition for obtaining any mining or petroleum exploration rights. Local content and environmental concerns have also been addressed.

The Petroleum Law applies to petroleum and to any infrastructure, belonging to or held by the holder of rights or third parties, used in connection with oil operations, subject to Mozambican law, including mobile infrastructure under a foreign flag located in Mozambique with the purpose of conducting or assisting in petroleum operations in a concession contract area, unless otherwise established by law.

This law also applies to the use and consumption of petroleum, when such use is necessary or forms an integral part of the operations of production or transportation of petroleum

It is excluded from the scope of this Law petroleum refining and its industrial use, distribution and commercialization of petroleum products. Since specific guidelines will be applicable to the projects of Natural Gas Liquefaction of Rovuma's Basin Areas 1 and 4 - to be approved by decree-law pursuant to legislative authorization recently approved by the Mozambican Parliament - the scope of the Petroleum Law may in practice be reduced (depending on the exceptions that such decree-law will bring to the Petroleum Law).

There is no specific mentioning about hydrogen in any of the mining laws in Mozambique and to the best of our knowledge no discussion amongst relevant ministries is ongoing.

3.3 South Africa

The regulatory framework governing the equitable access to and sustainable development of South Africa's natural mineral and petroleum resources is the Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act (MPRDA, Act No. 28, 2002) and the Mineral and Petroleum Development Regulations. The Act was amended by the Minerals and Energy Laws Amendment Act 11 of 2005 and the Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Amendment Act 49 of 2008. In this act, The Ministry of the Department of Minerals and Energy are the responsible authority for the implementation of environmental matters and specific legislation as described under the National Environmental Management Act, 1998 as it pertains to prospecting, mining, exploration, production and other related or incidental activities on an area demarked for prospecting, mining, exploration and/or production. The Mining titles Registration Act N0 16 of 1967 (MTRA) governs permits and rights granted under the MPRDA.

A new Upstream Petroleum Resources Development Bill was introduced to the South African National Assembly on 1 July 2021. The Upstream Petroleum Resources Development Act 23 of 2024 (UPRDA) was passed on 25 October 2024. The aim of this bill is to separate upstream oil and gas activities (including geological surveys, drilling and mining and manufacturing) from the mining sector and facilitate the orderly and equitable development of this resource to the benefit the citizens of South Africa.

In the MPDRA **petroleum** is defined as

*"any liquid, solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas** existing in a natural condition in the earth's crust and includes any such liquid or solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas**, which gas has in any manner been returned to such natural condition, but does not include coal, bituminous shale or other stratified deposits from which oil can be obtained by destructive distillation or gas arising from a marsh or other surface deposit"*

with an updated definition given in UPRDA as

*"any liquid, solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas** existing in a natural condition in the earth's crust, **and includes associated liquid or gas**, any liquid or solid hydrocarbon **or combustible gas**, but does not include coal, bituminous shale or other stratified deposits from which oil can be obtained by destructive distillation or gas arising from a marsh or other surface deposit"*,

however, **gas** is defined in UPRDA as

"any hydrocarbon which at a temperature of 21 degrees Celsius and a pressure of one atmosphere, is in a gaseous phase existing in a natural condition in the earth's crust, regardless of the nature of the host rock, and includes condensate of such gas, but does not include hydrocarbon gas obtained by destructive distillation or gas arising from a marsh or other surface deposit".

The Gas Act (Act No. 48 of 2001) defines **gas** as

*"hydrocarbon gases transported by pipeline, including natural gas, artificial gas, **hydrogen rich gas**, methane rich gas, synthetic gas, coal bed methane gas, liquefied natural gas, compressed natural gas, re-gasified liquefied natural gas, liquefied petroleum gas or any combination thereof"*

A **mineral** is defined in MPDRA as

*"any substance, whether in solid, liquid **or gaseous form**, occurring naturally in or on the earth or in or under water and which was formed by or subjected to a geological process,*

and includes sand, stone, rock, gravel, clay, soil and any mineral occurring in residue stockpiles or in residue deposits, but excludes-

(a) water, other than water taken from land or sea for the extraction of any mineral from such water;

(b) petroleum; or

(c) peat.”

As a combustible gas, using the definitions given above, natural hydrogen gas could therefore be considered as falling **within both petroleum AND mineral classifications**, and the relevant legislation is not clear. It is likely that legislation would need to be amended to make provision for upstream hydrogen resource development, and to help clarify whether natural hydrogen gas would fall under mineral or petroleum classification.

In both MPDRA and UPRDA, Chapter 6 provides the legislative framework for the exploration and production of petroleum in South Africa. MPDRA provides the legislative framework for the exploration and production of minerals.

References of the relevant legislation in South Africa:

- Act Act No. 23 of 2024: Upstream Petroleum Resources Development Act, Act 2024 (UPRDA). [Link](#).
- Act No 85 of 1993. Occupational Health and Safety Act, 1993. [Link](#).
- Act No. 107 of 1998: National Environmental Management Act, 1998. [Link](#).
- Act No. 11 of 2005: Minerals and Energy Laws Amendment Act, 2005. [Link](#).
- Act No. 15 of 2003: Explosives Act, 2003. [Link](#)
- Act No. 28 of 2002: Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act, 2002. [Link](#).
- Act No. 48 of 2001: Gas Act, 2001. [Link](#).
- Act No. 48 of 2001: Gas Act, 2001. [Link](#).
- Act No. 49 of 2008: Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Amendment Act, 2008. [Link](#).
- Altmann, M., Cloete, L., Diehl, L., Rubbers, E., Walwyn, D., Wurster, R., Zeiss, J. (2002) Regulations, Codes, and Standards in the Frame of Promoting the Development of a Hydrogen Economy for South Africa. Draft scoping Study for Deutsche Gesellschaft Fur Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GMBH. Preliminary Final Scoping Study Report, 8 July 2022.
- Emerging themese and priorities of green hydrogen research to support public and private sector objectives. 29 November 2023. Published by H2.SA (Green Hydrogen South Africa), Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH and South African National Energy Development Institute (SANEDI).
- Green Hydrogen Commercialization Strategy for South Africa FINAL REPORT 30 November 2022. [Link](#)
- Hydrogen Society Roadmap for South Africa 2021. Department of Science and Innovation. [Link](#).
- Occupational Health and Safety Act (85/1993): Construction Regulations, 2014. [Link](#).
- Occupational Health and Safety Act (85/1993): Hazardous Chemical Substances Regulations, 1995. [Link](#)
- Occupational Health and Safety Act (85/1993): Pressure Equipment Regulations, 2009. [Link](#).
- Occupational Health and Safety Act (85/1993): Regulations for Hazardous Chemical Agents 2021. [Link](#)

- Occupational Health and Safety Act (85/1993): Regulations for Hazardous Chemical Agents 2024 (under review). [Link](#)
- Occupational Health and Safety Act (85/1993): Regulations: Major Hazard Installations, 2001. [Link](#)
- Upstream Petroleum Resources Development Bill of 2021. [Link](#).

3.4 Togo

The regulatory framework for mining and hydrocarbon exploration in Togo aims to promote resource development while ensuring sustainability and balancing economic growth with environmental protection. The Ministry of Mines and Energy Resources oversees the management, exploration, and development of mineral and hydrocarbon resources. It is responsible for issuing permits, monitoring compliance, and enforcing regulations. The National Agency for Environmental Management (ANGE) plays a crucial role in ensuring environmental sustainability, conducting impact assessments, and monitoring project compliance. Additionally, Togo participates in the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI), which promotes transparency and accountability in revenues generated from the extractive industries.

The mining sector operates under the **Mining Code, established in 2011 and revised in 2019**. This legislation outlines procedures for granting exploration and exploitation permits, aiming to attract private investment while ensuring the state retains a share in strategic resources. Companies seeking exploration permits can operate for up to seven years to conduct geological surveys and feasibility studies, while exploitation licenses are issued for up to 25 years, renewable for an additional 10 years. The code also requires mining operators to pay royalties on extracted resources, contribute to community development, and implement environmental rehabilitation plans for mined areas.

The hydrocarbon sector is regulated by the **Hydrocarbon Code of 2014**, which governs exploration, production, and distribution. The code encourages foreign investment through production-sharing agreements (PSAs) and offers tax incentives for exploration activities. Exploration permits for hydrocarbons are valid for up to 10 years, with renewals, while production licenses typically last 25 years, depending on the project's lifespan. The government retains an equity stake in oil and gas projects through the Société Togolaise des Hydrocarbures (STH), ensuring state participation in the benefits. Environmental standards are strict, requiring operators to submit environmental impact studies and implement management plans to mitigate risks.

Environmental and social safeguards are integral to the regulatory framework. All projects must undergo Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) to identify potential risks and propose mitigation strategies. Companies are obligated to engage with local communities, address concerns related to displacement or resource use, and submit rehabilitation plans to restore natural ecosystems after project completion.

At a regional level, Togo aligns its policies with the ECOWAS Mining Directives, which aim to harmonize mining regulations across West Africa. Internationally, its commitment to the EITI ensures transparency, and its adherence to the Paris Agreement influences its approach to fossil fuel exploration by emphasizing greenhouse gas reduction targets.

Despite the comprehensive regulatory framework, Togo faces challenges such as limited enforcement capacity to monitor compliance, social tensions in mining-affected areas, and the ongoing need to balance economic development with environmental conservation.

Togo does not have a dedicated regulatory framework specifically for hydrogen production, storage, distribution, or utilization, including natural hydrogen exploration. However,

hydrogen as an energy carrier aligns with Togo's broader goals for energy transition, renewable energy expansion, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The National Development Plan (**Plan National de Développement 2018–2022**) emphasizes the transition to renewable energy source and although hydrogen is not explicitly mentioned, it could be included under broader renewable energy strategies as its potential role in decarbonization becomes more evident.

4. Gap Analysis

Mozambique and **Togo** legal framework do not make any mentioning of the natural hydrogen at all. Morocco also lacks any specific mentioning to hydrogen in its regulatory framework for the mining and hydrocarbon sectors, but lessons learned in the development of its ambitious green hydrogen strategy can be used to develop the appropriate regulatory framework. This means that in these countries, the subsector will need to advocate more for the designing of specific law or inclusion of the natural hydrogen in the petroleum law in order to regulate the subsector in terms of exploration and exploitation licensing.

The situation is somewhat different for **South Africa**, which does not specifically address natural hydrogen, but the existing legal framework for the minerals and petroleum sector does include provisions under which natural hydrogen could eventually be included. The gap analysis for natural hydrogen production for South Africa can be viewed under the grouping of upstream, midstream, and downstream industries. Upstream industries focus on geological surveys, mining, drilling, and manufacturing. The relevant legislative frameworks for minerals and petroleum are well described under MTRA (Act No. 28, 2002; No. 49, 2008) and UPRDA (Act No. 23, 2004) with a strong overlap with NEMA (Act No. 107, 1998). Once the ambiguity in the definitions of petroleum and minerals is clarified, allowing for the clear classification of natural hydrogen, the relevant regulatory framework should be followed. There remain extensive gaps in the available geological information and knowledge on the occurrence of hydrogen, and the potential existence of reservoirs large enough for economic exploitation. An increase in the knowledge and expertise around natural hydrogen in South Africa will address any gaps in interest from mainstream government, research, energy providers and regulators, funding, and manufacturing industries.

The natural hydrogen mid-stream industry (e.g., storage, transportation including pipelines, rail, and truck), and downstream industry (distribution of product, and retail outlets) overlap with many of the same industries as green hydrogen. Several investigations focus on gap analysis for green hydrogen. Altmann et al (2002, pp.3-31) concentrated on the transport sector, particularly refueling, looking at the refueling processes for road vehicles and trains, hydrogen transportation (pipeline) and onsite storage, including certification schemes for quality and compliance purposes, and homologation of hydrogen road vehicles including Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEV's). Gaps identified include general legislation for refueling purposes and homologation, and the capacity capabilities of existing infrastructure. There exists no South African National Standards (SANS) for any H₂ process. Various regulations covering occupational health and safety (Act No. 85 of 1993), hazardous chemical agents (Hazardous Chemical Substances Regulations, 1995 amended by the Regulations for Hazardous Chemical Agents 2021, and under review in 2024), pressure equipment (Pressure Equipment Regulations, 2009), construction (Construction Regulations, 2014), explosive (Explosives Act No. 15, 2003), and major hazard installation (Major Hazard Installations, 2001), can be also be applied to the natural hydrogen process. Although the Gas Act (No. 48, 2001) does include "combustible gas" the UPRDA only refers to hydrocarbons, effectively excluding hydrogen gas.

A report on emerging themes and priorities in support of public and private sector objectives (2023) also provides an overview of the green hydrogen value chain, current research, and gaps that different public and private entities can fill.

The Hydrogen Society Roadmap (2021), under auspice of the Department of Science, Technology, and Innovation (DSTI), aims to connect a variety of public and private stakeholders and institutions to help develop, deploy, and use hydrogen and hydrogen related technologies as part of our economic development and the country's commitment of reducing carbon emissions. This roadmap strives for an understanding of the South African Hydrogen opportunity and the potential future of Hydrogen in South Africa. The report on the Green Hydrogen Commercialization Strategy for South Africa (2022) can be used as a starting point and guideline for the commercialization opportunities for natural hydrogen.

The study has concluded that in the four target countries there are adequate institutions that can promote and regulate natural hydrogen, and HyAfrica can play a role in raising awareness about the resource and about the need for specific regulation.

The four target countries do not have experience yet in the exploration, evaluation and exploitation of natural hydrogen. In Morocco, South Africa and Mozambique there are motivated researching institutions that that can promote and evaluate natural hydrogen, but none of the countries and institutions have yet defined natural hydrogen research as a priority and appropriate laboratories and research facilities (such as laboratories for gas analysis) have yet to be established.

